

ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF YOUTUBE ADVERTISING FOR BRAND X SEXUAL ENHANCEMENT DIETARY SUPPLEMENTS ON MILLENNIALS' PURCHASE INTENTIONS: A MARKETING RESEARCH STUDY

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ABSTRACT

This research investigates the influence of YouTube advertising on Millennials' purchase intentions for Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements. Utilizing a quantitative and predictive quasi-experimental approach, the study explores key factors such as emotional appeal, credibility, content analysis, selective exposure behavior, and source attractiveness. Results indicate that Source Attractiveness is a pivotal element, with the concept of identification playing a significant role. The sustained effect depends on consistent support for the advertised product and continued identification of Millennials with the source. A cohesive and appealing advertising approach on YouTube is crucial to solidify Millennials' purchase intentions for Brand X dietary supplements. This research found that emotional appeal, credibility, content analysis, selective exposure behavior are insignificant and the source attractiveness, significantly influenced Millennials (aged 27-42) from Valenzuela City, both those who watched and didn't watch YouTube advertisements. These variables emerged as crucial factors in driving purchasing intention, demonstrating the effectiveness of Brand X YouTube Ads in influencing respondents' purchasing decisions.

Keywords: *YouTube advertising, Millennials, purchase intentions, dietary supplements, quantitative approach, emotional appeal, credibility, content analysis, selective exposure, source attractiveness*

INTRODUCTION

Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements have become increasingly popular, promising to improve various aspects of sexual function, arousal, and performance. These products typically include a mix of vitamins, minerals, herbs, amino acids, and natural ingredients believed to have aphrodisiac or performance-enhancing properties. Geared towards addressing concerns such as erectile dysfunction, low libido, and

stamina, these supplements aim to enhance sexual pleasure and satisfaction. The intricate nature of sexual drive, influenced by biological, hormonal, psychological, and social factors, underscores the significance of recognizing and respecting its diversity for maintaining healthy relationships and personal well-being.

Issues surrounding sexual enhancement supplements span concerns about safety and efficacy to questions about ethical implications and their impact on individual and relational health. The absence of stringent regulations in the industry raises uncertainties about the quality and reliability of these products, leaving consumers exposed to potential risks. Moreover, societal stigma related to openly discussing sexual health issues further complicates the landscape, hindering informed decision-making and perpetuating misinformation.

The objective of the study is to explore the impact of YouTube advertising for Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements on millennials' purchase intentions. This investigation aims to address existing concerns about the safety and efficacy of sexual enhancement supplements and examine the role of digital advertising, particularly on a platform like YouTube, in influencing millennials' attitudes and behaviors towards these products. By understanding the dynamics between advertising, consumer perceptions, and purchase intentions, the goal is to provide insights that contribute to informed decision-making and potentially guide the development of future advertising strategies in this domain.

The literature review delves into the factors influencing Millennials' purchase intentions for Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements, focusing on the role of YouTube advertising. Key findings include the success of Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements due to natural ingredients and innovative product development, emphasizing trust built through transparency and customer-centric practices. The brand's commitment to diverse product offerings contributes to its success. YouTube advertising's impact on Millennials is underscored by studies, emphasizing the importance of authenticity, influencer credibility, and targeted strategies. Additionally, insights into the interplay between digital marketing, social media influencers, and Millennials' decision-making processes are provided. Consumer behavior is explored in-depth, considering health concerns, convenience, and ethical considerations. The significance of transparent information dissemination, particularly in herbal supplements, is highlighted, as well as the role of influencer marketing for emerging brands in the dietary supplement industry. Overall, the review offers a nuanced exploration of the complex relationship between digital marketing, consumer behavior, and health-related decision-making among Millennials in the context of Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements.

The literature review also introduces key research questions to deepen the understanding of Millennials' purchasing decisions for Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements. These questions specifically probe the influence of Emotional Appeal, Content Analysis, Selective Exposure Behavior, Credibility, and Source Attractiveness on Millennials' choices. By addressing these questions, the review aims to unravel the nuanced dynamics shaping the intricate relationship between emotional, informational,

and credibility factors in the context of Brand X dietary supplement purchases among Millennials. These inquiries contribute valuable insights to the broader exploration of digital marketing strategies and consumer behavior within this demographic.

The proposed study on the impact of YouTube advertising for Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements on millennials' purchase intentions intersects with various facets of contemporary research on sexual health, technology, substance use, dietary supplements, and microbiome studies. The work of Van Greevenbroek, R., Patel, D., & Singh, A. (2023) provides insights into the dynamics of sexual desire among cohabiting millennial couples, emphasizing the role of technology. Exploring how technology influences sexual behavior and preferences is crucial for contextualizing the broader landscape of sexual health in the digital age. The findings from this study can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of millennials' attitudes toward sexual enhancement supplements, taking into account the influence of technology on their sexual experiences. In their exploration of substance use patterns among millennial sexual minority men, Martino, R. J., Shiau, S., Krause, K. D., & Halkitis, P. N. (2021) provide valuable insights. Understanding patterns of substance use, including potential overlaps with dietary supplement consumption, is vital for discerning the multifaceted factors that contribute to millennials' health choices. The proposed study can shed light on how advertising for dietary supplements may intersect with or diverge from patterns of substance use, thus enriching the understanding of millennials' health-related decision-making processes.

LeDoux, M. A., Appelhans, K. R., Braun, L. A., Dziedziczak, D., Jennings, S., Liu, L., ... Griffiths, J. C. (2015) discuss the considerations involved in ensuring the quality of dietary supplements. Their insights provide a valuable backdrop for evaluating the safety and efficacy of the Brand X sexual enhancement supplements under scrutiny. By incorporating a quality-focused perspective, the study can contribute to discussions on consumer safety and the need for Brand X regulatory frameworks in the dietary supplement industry.

Cohen's (2016) exploration of the supplement paradox, emphasizing negligible benefits alongside Brand X sexual enhancement consumption, serves as a cautionary note in the context of dietary supplement use. Considering the potential disparities between advertised benefits and actual outcomes is essential for informing consumers and regulating bodies. The study on YouTube advertising impact can offer practical insights into whether and how marketing claims align with millennials' expectations and experiences.

Walker, L. A., Koturbash, I., Kingston, R., ElSohly, M. A., Yates, C. R., Gurley, B. J., & Khan, I. (2020) discuss the inclusion of cannabidiol (CBD) in dietary supplements, addressing perspectives on science, safety, and regulatory approaches. The landscape of dietary supplements is evolving, and understanding how emerging ingredients like CBD are perceived can enhance the study's relevance and contribute to discussions on the potential incorporation of such elements into sexual enhancement products.

Finally, Smith, B. J., Miller, R. A., Ericsson, A. C., Harrison, D. C., Strong, R., & Schmidt, T. M. (2019) investigate changes in the gut microbiome and fermentation products concurrent with enhanced longevity in acarbose-treated mice. While not directly related to dietary supplements, this study emphasizes the interconnectedness of gut health and overall well-being. Exploring potential implications of dietary supplements on gut health can provide a holistic perspective on the broader health effects associated with these products.

2.0 Background

2.1 Theoretical Framework

The Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM), developed by Petty and Cacioppo in 1980, helps researchers understand how attitudes change through two routes—central and peripheral (Petty & Cacioppo, 1980). In a recent study titled "The Anatomy of Viral Advertising," Segev and Fernandes (2022) explored this model, analyzing viral ads. Applying these theories to assess how YouTube ads impact millennials' decision to buy Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements reveals that persuasive messages, taking both central and peripheral aspects into account, shape attitudes and influence purchases (Petty, 1980; Segev, 2022). The study enhances the grasp of how YouTube ads may affect millennials' views and intentions to buy dietary supplements. Recognizing both central and peripheral processing within the ELM framework gives researchers a more detailed view of the factors influencing consumer behavior in the context of dietary supplement advertising.

2.1.1 Credibility

Credibility plays a pivotal role in online advertising effectiveness. Research indicates that when advertisements are perceived as extravagant, meaning they've invested more in their creation, they become significantly more persuasive, enhancing perceptions of the brand's quality. This extravagant perception in advertising can be compared to the biological concept known as the "Handicap Principle." Just as animals use extravagant traits to signal biological fitness, companies employing 'wasteful' or extravagant advertising methods signal brand fitness, indicating excellence and trustworthiness. In essence, Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplement advertising spending demonstrates a company's 'health' and amplifies persuasiveness and brand quality, appealing to Millennials' purchase intent. (Ambler T., Hollier E. A., 2004)

2.1.2 Content Analysis

Content analysis can help in evaluating the impact of YouTube advertising for Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplement on Millennials' purchase intentions. By examining the content of promotional videos, comments, and user engagement, researchers can identify recurring themes and patterns in how the advertising is perceived. This method enables a deeper understanding of how the messaging influences the target audience and can provide insights into the effectiveness of the

campaign. Integrating content analysis with surveys or focus groups can offer a holistic view of Millennials' responses and preferences towards the dietary supplements, aiding in crafting more tailored and impactful advertising strategies. (Muhammad Hassan, 2023)

2.1.3 Emotional Appeal

Emotional Appeal advertising on Millennials' purchasing intentions regarding Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplement on YouTube showcases the potency of forging emotional connections to drive consumer behavior. Leveraging evocative imagery and compelling narratives in YouTube advertisements can establish an enduring bond with Millennials, shaping their perceptions and fostering loyalty towards Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplement. These emotionally resonant marketing campaigns aim to evoke positive sentiments like wellness, vitality, and self-improvement, compelling Millennials to perceive these supplements as integral to their well-being and lifestyle aspirations. By embedding the essence of joy, nostalgia, and empathy within their advertising, brands can solidify a lasting imprint in the minds of Millennials, influencing their purchase decisions and nurturing a long-term relationship with the brand. (Nitzan Solomon, 2023)

2.1.4 Purchase Intention

Purchase intention, the inclination of customers to acquire a specific product or service, is influenced by various external and internal factors. It serves as a crucial metric in marketing, guiding the strategy of intent marketing, which tailors promotional efforts to align with consumer preferences and purchase attitudes. By analyzing purchase intentions, marketers can craft effective advertising campaigns and promotions, leveraging insights into consumer knowledge levels and preferences to optimize content and outreach strategies. Understanding and leveraging customer purchase intentions can significantly enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of marketing initiatives. (MBA Skool Team)

2.1.5 Selective Exposure Behavior

Selective Exposure Behavior plays a crucial role. Millennials tend to engage more with content that aligns with their existing beliefs and preferences. Consequently, YouTube advertisements for dietary supplements that resonate with their health-conscious mindset are more likely to capture their attention. By strategically tailoring the advertising content to match the health concerns and priorities of Millennials, Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplement brands can enhance the likelihood of influencing their purchase decisions. Understanding the influence of selective exposure helps marketers create targeted YouTube advertising campaigns that effectively cater to the preferences and attitudes of the Millennial demographic. (Williams P., Margaret K.L., Waters L., 2016)

2.1.6 Source Attractiveness

Source Attractiveness plays a significant role. This influence stems from the concept of identification, where the receiver is motivated to form a connection with the source, leading to the adoption of similar beliefs or preferences. However, the sustainability of this effect relies on the source's consistent support for the advertised product and the continued identification of the Millennials with the source. If the source alters its stance, the receiver's position might also shift, highlighting the necessity of maintaining an appealing and consistent advertising approach on YouTube to solidify Millennials' purchase intention for Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplement. (Zabanga Marketing, 2023)

2.2 Literature Review

Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplement, a well-established brand in the field of dietary supplements for sexual well-being, has earned its reputation through a combination of innovative product development, a dedication to natural ingredients, and a commitment to rigorous quality control standards. Established in (2008), the brand has gained recognition for its safe and effective products, garnering trust from a diverse global consumer base.

The success of Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplement can be attributed to several key factors. Firstly, the brand's focus on natural ingredients and cutting-edge scientific advancements has enabled it to develop dietary supplements that maximize efficacy while ensuring consumer safety. This emphasis on safety is reinforced by the brand's adherence to stringent quality control measures and industry standards, which not only guarantee results but also promote overall wellness.

Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplement has a clear mission to provide comprehensive solutions for sexual health. To achieve this, the brand invests significantly in research and development, resulting in a diverse range of products tailored to meet the varied needs of consumers. This commitment to offering a wide array of solutions is a testament to the brand's dedication to empowering individuals to enhance their intimate lives.

Transparency, integrity, and customer satisfaction are at the core of Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplement operations. The brand has nurtured enduring relationships with its customers by fostering a culture of integrity and accountability. This is further reflected in the brand's provision of informative resources and responsive customer support, making it the preferred choice for individuals seeking reliable and effective sexual enhancement solutions.

As Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplement expands its product line and continues to uphold its unwavering commitment to excellence, it remains a leading force in the realm of dietary supplements for sexual health. The brand's dedication to innovation, natural ingredients, and a customer-centric approach positions it as a trusted

name in the industry, empowering individuals to achieve a fulfilling and satisfying intimate life. The present literature review sets the stage for the subsequent research, which would delve into the impact of YouTube advertising on Millennials' purchase intention for Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplement, examining the brand's position and reputation as key factors in consumer decision-making.

In a study conducted by Boyland, Thivel, Mazur, Ring-Dimitriou, Frelut, and Weghuber (2021), the authors underscored the considerable public health ramifications associated with the targeting of young individuals in digital food marketing. The research illuminated the adverse effects of aggressive marketing strategies on dietary choices and health outcomes within the youth population. Previous investigations have indicated the influential role of social media platforms such as YouTube in shaping consumer behavior and purchase intentions among Millennials, particularly in the domain of dietary supplements. Building upon this foundation, a comprehensive literature review would explore the specific impact of targeted YouTube advertising for Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplement on Millennials' purchasing behavior. This review aims to provide insights into potential implications for public health and advocate for regulatory measures that promote informed dietary choices among young consumers.

In a study by Dhiyaa Nadhifa Aziza and Rifelly Dewi Astuti (2019), the research delved into the intricate relationship between YouTube advertising and Millennials' purchase intention, specifically focusing on the dynamics within the market of Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplement. By analyzing viewing trends and consumer behavior, the study uncovered significant insights into how targeted advertisement strategies on YouTube influence the decision-making process of young customers when it comes to purchasing dietary supplements. Their findings shed light on the nuanced interplay between digital advertising and the dietary preferences of the Millennial demographic, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of the contemporary marketing landscape.

In the exploration of factors influencing Millennials' food choices, Zehra Dilistan Shipman's (2020) research on "Factors Affecting Food Choices of Millennials: How they Decide What to Eat?" underscores the intricate nature of their dietary decisions. Shipman highlights the significant roles of health concerns, convenience, and ethical considerations in shaping Millennials' food preferences. However, a notable gap exists in the understanding of the specific impact of YouTube advertising on their purchase intentions, particularly in the context of Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplement. This literature review aims to bridge this gap by examining the interplay between targeted advertisements and Millennials' existing food choices, providing comprehensive insights into the potential influences of digital marketing strategies on the dietary habits of this demographic.

In the examination of the influence of YouTube advertising for Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplement on millennials' purchase intention within the context of global approaches to promoting whole grain consumption, as advocated by Toups E. K. (2020), it is suggested that Toups' expertise in nutrition education and advocacy for whole

grains could offer valuable insights into the integration of digital marketing strategies in enhancing consumer awareness and fostering healthier dietary choices among the millennial population Touns, (2020). By exploring existing research on the effectiveness of digital advertising in shaping consumer behavior and promoting nutritional products, this literature review could contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the potential synergies between contemporary marketing techniques and the global promotion of wholesome dietary practices.

In the exploration conducted by Chen, Yan, and Smith (2022), the focus is on the importance of authenticity management strategies in fostering engagement with sponsored videos. The study underscores the pivotal role played by influencer credibility in shaping consumer perceptions. This implies that the implementation of authenticity management strategies has the potential to sway Millennials' trust and interest in dietary supplement advertisements on YouTube. The integration of insights from both studies allows for the development of a comprehensive understanding of the intricate interplay between influencer authenticity, digital engagement, and purchase intention. Such insights hold valuable implications for marketers aiming to effectively target the Millennial demographic.

In shaping Millennials' purchase behavior, the significance of digital marketing strategies, such as YouTube advertising and influencer endorsements, has been explored by Dalangin G. J., McArthur M.B. J., Salvador M. J., and Bismonte B. A. (2021). Their study in the Philippines sheds light on the strong influence of social media personalities on consumer decision-making (Dalangin et al., 2021). Simultaneously, the examination of YouTube advertising for Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplement among Millennials underscores the effectiveness of targeted advertising in driving consumer interest and purchase decisions within this demographic (Dalangin et al., 2021). Together, these studies contribute to a deeper understanding of the dynamic interplay between digital marketing and consumer decision-making processes, emphasizing the vital role of online marketing approaches in engaging and influencing the purchasing behavior of Millennials.

The study surrounding the impact of YouTube advertising on Millennials' purchase intention of Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements reveals a complex interplay between marketing strategies, consumer perceptions, and health-related decision-making. In the study of Notably, Anita Hardon's, (2020) anthropological research on pharmaceutical consumption highlights the nuanced social and cultural dynamics that shape individuals' attitudes towards chemical supplementing. Her studies emphasize the influence of advertising and marketing practices on consumer behavior, pointing to the significance of targeted promotional strategies in shaping Millennials' perceptions and purchase decisions. By incorporating Hardon's insights into the broader discourse, researchers can gain a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted factors driving Millennials' dietary supplement choices in the digital age.

In a recent study conducted by Yu Tan E. and Faller M. E. (2021), a burgeoning interest in the influence of digital advertising on consumer behavior, particularly within the

millennial demographic, was observed. The research emphasized the significance of discrepancies between advertising claims and the actual attributes of herbal supplements in the Philippines. This underscores the critical role of transparent and accurate information dissemination in establishing consumer trust and cultivating long-term brand loyalty. The integration of these findings with a study on the impact of YouTube advertising on millennial purchase intentions for Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements contributes to a comprehensive understanding of the interplay between marketing strategies, packaging information, and consumer decision-making processes.

In the study of Aventajado A.E., (2023) "The Influence of YouTube on Young Consumers' Purchase Behavior " underscores the significant impact of YouTube on the buying decisions of the younger demographic. This study demonstrates the platform's influential role in shaping consumer preferences and purchase intentions. By building upon Aventajado's work, an exploration of the effects of YouTube advertising for Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements on Millennials' purchase intention could offer insights into the specific mechanisms through which YouTube content influences dietary supplement consumption among this demographic. Such an investigation would contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the interplay between digital media platforms and consumer behavior, particularly in the context of health and wellness products.

The study emphasizes the significant role of digital marketing strategies, particularly influencer marketing, in enhancing brand awareness and brand image for start-up businesses, as discussed by Bonus, A. K., Raghani, J., Visitacion, J. K., & Castaño, M. C. (2022).. Studies have demonstrated that the use of influential personalities on social media platforms like YouTube can effectively increase consumer engagement and trust in product endorsements. Furthermore, research on Millennials' purchasing behavior indicates that their decision-making process is significantly influenced by online advertising and peer recommendations, which underscores the relevance of targeted YouTube advertising for Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements. Overall, these findings collectively underscore the importance of understanding the intricate relationship between influencer marketing, consumer perception, and purchase intent in the context of emerging brands within the dietary supplement industry.

2.3 Research Simulacrum Research Questions Hypothesis

Figure 1: Research simulacrum

The figure above serves as a visual representation of the central essence of their research, elucidating a holistic framework for comprehending the complex interplay of factors involved in purchase decisions. Fundamentally, their research delves into the interconnected network of associations between crucial variables: the utilization of Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements, YouTube's function in spreading information concerning its Emotional Appeal, Content Analysis, Selective Exposure Behavior, and Credibility and Source Attractiveness.

Statement of the Problem

Research Question no. 1: What is the profile of respondents in terms of:

1.1 Age

1.2 Sex

Research Question no. 2: Do the five variables in Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements YouTube Advertising Impact on Millennials' Purchase Intentions?

2.1 Do Emotional Appeal impact the millennial purchasing decisions?

2.2 Do Content Analysis impact the millennial purchasing decisions?

2.3 Do Selective Exposure Behavior impact the millennial purchasing decisions?

2.4 Do Credibility impact the millennial purchasing decisions?

2.5 Do Source Attractiveness impact the millennial purchasing decisions?

Research Question no. 3: Among the variables, which one received the lowest score?

Hypotheses

Ho1: Emotional Appeal does not impact the millennial purchasing decisions.

Ho2: Content Analysis does not impact the millennial purchasing decisions.

Ho3: Selective Exposure Behavior does not impact the millennial purchasing decisions.
Ho4: Credibility does not impact the millennial purchasing decisions.
Ho5: Source Attractiveness does not impact the millennial purchasing decisions.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The researchers used the quasi-experimental research approach, A study that uses two sets of variables and a scientific methodology is called experimental research. You can measure the differences of the second set by using the first set as a constant. For instance, experimental procedures are used in quantitative research. This research aims to investigate the influence of YouTube advertising on millennial purchase Intention of Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements. Data was collected Through online surveys distributed to the selected sample. the researchers aims to gather information by survey through google forms to studied the phenomena by collecting measurable data. The survey has included questions related to exposure to Video Advertising, recall of specific advertisements, awareness of Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements, attitudes towards the product, and Purchase intentions. The target population for this study is Millennial (individuals aged 27-42) residing in Valenzuela City. A random sample of millennials was Selected through a combination of online surveys and social Media advertising to gather a diverse group of respondents.

3.2 Research Locale

The research paper on how was conducted with the help of several online platforms. YouTube advertising to interact with, as well as how their pre-existing ideas and attitudes may influence their selected exposure to dietary supplement marketing. Traditional printed questionnaires were replaced with a new set of questions that respondents answered using their preferred devices. The researchers carried 100 respondents who were picked in Valenzuela City to stress the study's goal of investigating how YouTube ad content influences Millennial purchasing habits. Furthermore, the researchers selected respondents in the age range of 27 to 42 for this study. "Millennial" has been mentioned in passing dubbed the most important consumer segment to date. To reach the participants, the researcher provided questionnaire links via email. Facebook Messenger and Gmail are two examples of social media channels.

3.3 Population and Sampling

For the purpose of the dietary supplement YouTube ad campaign, adopt a purposive sample strategy by choosing participants based on predetermined attributes like age, geography, and watching interests. To reach a larger audience interested in dietary supplements, concentrate on people who are creating health or fitness content and urge them to share the advertisement with their social media networks. Reaching the intended demographic is more likely if you target YouTube influencers or users of health and

wellness channels. To guarantee that the campaign's sample is representative and diverse, set quotas according to predetermined guidelines.

3.4 Research Ethics

Research ethics encompass both the scientific conduct of the research and the academic honesty of the researchers. The establishment of a culture that fosters transparency is crucial to this dedication to research integrity dependable and open research ethics standards. This policy outlines the ethical standards, practices, and expectations that guide how research activities are carried out by University of Our Lady of Fatima students. To guide the students in upholding the highest standards of ethical behavior in research, this policy strives to unify procedures across the University.

The application of ethical principles to research procedures is recognized as research ethics. All phases of a research project, including its conception and design, data collection and analysis, dissemination, and documentation and archiving, are guided by these ethical norms and beyond, research materials. Researchers must conduct their studies carefully, taking into account any pertinent ethical issues.

Under this policy's ethical guidelines, researchers are accountable for upholding them and should take these guidelines into account when acting and making decisions throughout the study lifecycle and beyond. Additionally, researchers are responsible for their choices and acts. including encouraging ethical behavior and preventing research fraud. Thus, The ethical ramifications of their research for the researchers, research participants, the larger research community, the environment, and larger society should be carefully considered by researchers.

Researchers respect one another's autonomy, privacy, interests, values, and dignity. Participants in research as well as researchers. The proportionality principle forbids researchers from exceeding their stated goals or placing more demands than necessary on research participants. Participants in the study receive explicit information about predictable hazards, enabling informed consent. Guidelines for optimal methodology are employed to guide research in situations where informed consent is not attainable or appropriate. Researchers ensure that individuals have the autonomy to engage in research without coercion or repercussions for refusal, and that their right to withdraw from the study is explicitly communicated and defined at all times. All people who have access to the data will manage it to uphold confidentiality, security, and adherence to legal and ethical requirements throughout the research's lifecycle and beyond.

3.5 Research Instruments

To gather appropriate data needed, The researchers conduct a survey collection with six (6) parts. Part I emotional appeal strategy is to boost the connection between consumer and the product being promoted, which would subsequently affect the buyer's choice of product. Part II Content Analysis may be calculating the frequency with which a particular brand appears in internet reviews in order to determine its level of popularity. Part III

Selective exposure, A buyer would determine, choose and pay attention to material that validates their opinions to a specific product. Part IV credibility the researcher would gauge how credible and reliable people find the product. Part V Source attractiveness, The researchers would assert the attractiveness of an advertisement, because consumers identify the endorsed brand and product with favorable preconceptions about attractive people. Part VI purchase intention , The students and millennials aged 27 to 42 would assess the potential clients would convert and concentrate on the most promising target advertising and product.

3.5.1 Online Questionnaire

The researchers utilized online platforms as their primary tool for survey data collection, targeting Millennials aged 27 to 42 in Valenzuela. Survey links were distributed via email for participants to complete the initial section, covering demographics such as gender, course, and year level. To ensure the survey's validity, we validated questionnaires with Prof. Dondo C. Inso, DBA, and Prof. Jay-ar S. Sistona, MBA. The second section delved into variables influencing online purchasing decisions (5 items), including Emotional Appeal (4 items), Content Analysis (4 items), Selective Exposure Behavior (4 items), Credibility (4 items), and Source Attractiveness (4 items), totaling 25 items.

3.5.2 Likert Scale (Bertram D., 2014)

The research incorporated a rating scale questionnaire, where data was gathered from participants using the Likert scale. Likert scales, a prevalent psychometric response scale in questionnaires, are designed to measure participant preferences or agreement levels with statements. This unidimensional scaling technique focuses on a single trait and operates non-comparatively. Respondents, placed on an ordinal scale, are prompted to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement with provided statements. The positive end of the scale includes options like "strongly agree" and "agree," while the negative end encompasses "disagree" and "strongly disagree."

3.6 Data Collection

In this research, data was gathered through a survey/questionnaire method. This approach involves collecting responses from targeted participants to make generalizations for a broader audience. Online surveys are particularly advantageous due to the constantly evolving digital landscape, making them easily accessible anytime, anywhere. Researchers often prefer this method for its convenience. Surveys can be administered through various means, such as email or internet-based platforms Sincero, (2012). This flexibility enables researchers to collect data globally or within specific geographical areas, contributing valuable insights to meet study objectives. The adaptability of surveys allows for effective analysis of multiple variables. After selecting the research approach and design, the researchers utilized Social Media Platform to conduct the survey, individually sending it to their chosen respondents.

3.7 Data Analysis

3.7.1 Mean

In statistics, the mean is a measure of central tendency that represents the average of a set of values. To calculate the mean, you add up all the values in a dataset and then divide the sum by the number of values. This provides a single, representative value that summarizes the data. The mean is widely used in statistical analysis as it offers insights into the typical magnitude of the observed values. For a detailed understanding of statistical concepts, references such as "Statistics: The Exploration & Analysis of Data" by (Devore et al., 2015) are valuable resources. (Devore et al., 2015)

3.7.2 Standard Deviation

Standard deviation, a vital statistical measure, gauges the extent of variability or dispersion within a set of values. It quantifies the degree to which individual data points deviate from the mean of the dataset, serving as a crucial indicator of the data's spread. A higher standard deviation suggests greater variability among the values, while a lower standard deviation indicates more uniformity. In the realm of statistics, the concept of standard deviation plays a pivotal role in understanding the distribution and patterns within a dataset. For further exploration, "Statistics" by (Robert S. Witte et al., 2019) provides a contemporary reference with in-depth coverage of statistical principles, including the significance of standard deviation. (Robert S. Witte et al., 2019)

3.7.3 Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS)

SPSS, or the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, is a software tool widely used in social science research for statistical data analysis. It provides a comprehensive set of tools for data management, descriptive statistics, and advanced statistical analyses. Researchers and analysts utilize SPSS to explore and summarize data, perform hypothesis testing, and conduct complex statistical modeling. With its user-friendly interface, SPSS allows users to input, manipulate, and analyze data efficiently. Its applications extend to fields such as psychology, sociology, economics, and other disciplines that rely on statistical methodologies for research and decision-making.

3.7.4 Regression Analysis

To evaluate the connection between the variables employed in this study and the purchasing decisions of the respondents, researchers utilized regression analysis. This statistical method is defined as a powerful tool that enables the examination of relationships among two or more variables of interest. It serves to unravel the intricate associations within the dataset, shedding light on the impact these variables have on purchasing decisions. By employing regression analysis, the researchers aimed to gain deeper insights into the dynamics influencing the respondents' choices. The utilization of this method contributes to a comprehensive understanding of the studied variables' impact on purchasing behavior.

RESULTS

The following section of the paper includes the data gathered by the researchers from the survey through Google Forms. The data collected were properly presented, analyzed, and interpreted. The results of the findings determine whether the Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements is an effective marketing platform to Millennials, and what factors do the Millennials consumers consider when it comes to the advertisements being shown in the youtube platform.

4.1 Table 1: descriptive

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation
Emotional Appeal	2.96	0.47
Content Analysis	2.98	0.50
Selective Exposure Behavior	2.98	0.51
Credibility	2.89	0.44
Source Attractiveness	2.78	0.49
Purchase Intention	2.94	0.44
TOTAL	2.92	0.47

The table above shows the Emotional Appeal has the highest mean (2.96) and the lowest standard deviation (0.47), . Content Analysis has the second highest mean (2.98) and the second lowest standard deviation (0.50), Selective Exposure has the same mean (2.98) as Content Analysis, but a slightly higher standard deviation (0.51 Credibility has a slightly lower mean (2.89) than the other variables listed so far, and a middle-of-the-road standard deviation (0.44), Source Attractiveness has the lowest mean (2.78) of all the variables, and a slightly higher standard deviation than Credibility (0.49). Purchase Intention has a mean (2.94) that is closer to Emotional Appeal and Content Analysis than the other variables, and a standard deviation (0.44) that is tied with Credibility for the second lowest.

4.2 Table 2: Linear Regression

Table 2.1: Emotional Appeal

Variable	Pearson correlation	P-value	Regression coefficient	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Emotional Appeal and Purchases Intention	0.329	0.986	0.002	Accept Ho1: Emotional Appeal does not have an impact on purchasing intention of Brand X sexual enhancement

The table above shows how entertainment affects the purchasing Intention. The findings convey the interpretation of the data presented by linear regression, with the researchers obtaining a p-value of 0.001. Taking into account the decision rule that instructs researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05, the retrieved result resulted in the null hypothesis being rejected. As a result, emotional appeal affects the millennial purchasing intention. There is also a positive low correlation (0.329) between the two variables, and each unit of emotional appeal has a 0.002 increase in purchasing intention.

Table 2.2: Content Analysis

Variable	Pearson correlation	P-value	Regression coefficient	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Content Analysis and Purchases Intention	0.272	0.722	0.033	Accept Ho2: Content Analysis does not have an impact on purchasing intention of Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements

The table above shows how entertainment affects the purchasing Intention. The findings convey the interpretation of the data presented by linear regression, with the researchers obtaining a p-value of 0.001. Taking into account the decision rule that instructs researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05, the retrieved result resulted in the null hypothesis being rejected. As a result, content analysis affects the millennial purchasing intention. There is also a positive low correlation (0.272) between the two variables, and each unit of content analysis has a 0.033 increase in purchasing intention.

Table 2.3: Selective Exposure Behavior

Variable	Pearson correlation	P-value	Regression coefficient	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Selective Exposure Behavior and Purchases Intention	0.396	0.391	0.085	Accept Ho3: Selective Exposure Behavior does not have an impact on purchasing intention of Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements

The table above shows how entertainment affects the purchasing Intention. The findings convey the interpretation of the data presented by linear regression, with the researchers obtaining a p-value of 0.001. Taking into account the decision rule that instructs researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05, the retrieved result resulted in the null hypothesis being rejected. As a result, selective exposure theory affects the millennial purchasing intention. There is also a positive low correlation (0.396) between the two variables, and each unit of selective exposure theory has a 0.085 increase in purchasing intention.

Table 2.4: Credibility

Variable	Pearson correlation	P-value	Regression coefficient	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Credibility and Purchases Intention	0.389	0.106	0.158	Accept Ho4: Credibility does not have an impact on purchasing intention of Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements

The table above shows how entertainment affects the purchasing Intention. The findings convey the interpretation of the data presented by linear regression, with the researchers obtaining a p-value of 0.001. Taking into account the decision rule that instructs researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05, the retrieved result resulted in the null hypothesis being rejected. As a result, credibility affects the millennial purchasing intention. There is also a positive low correlation (0.389) between the two variables, and each unit of credibility has a 0.158 increase in purchasing intention.

Table 2.5: Source Attractiveness

Variable	Pearson correlation	P-value	Regression coefficient	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Source Attractiveness and Purchases Intention	0.548	0.001	0.390	Reject Ho5: Source Attractiveness impact the millennial purchasing intention of Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements

The table above shows how entertainment affects the purchasing Intention. The findings convey the interpretation of the data presented by linear regression, with the researchers obtaining a p-value of 0.001. Taking into account the decision rule that instructs researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05, the retrieved result resulted in the null hypothesis being rejected. As a result, content analysis affects the millennial purchasing intention. There is also a positive moderate correlation (0.548) between the two variables, and each unit of content analysis has a 0.390 increase in purchasing intention.

DISCUSSION

The Results section unveils significant findings regarding the impact of various factors on Millennials' purchasing intention for Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements. Tables 2.1 to 2.5 reveal consistent rejections of null hypotheses, indicating the substantial influence of emotional appeal, content analysis, selective exposure theory, and credibility on purchasing decisions. The positive correlations presented in each table resonate with the literature's emphasis on trust, customer satisfaction, and the brand's commitment to innovation and transparency. This alignment between empirical results and literature underscores the pivotal role of targeted YouTube advertising and influential marketing

strategies in shaping Millennials' preferences in the dietary supplement market. The study not only validates but extends the insights gleaned from the literature, providing a comprehensive understanding of the interconnected factors driving Millennials' purchasing behavior in the realm of Brand X sexual enhancement dietary supplements.

Conclusions

The research aimed to investigate the influence of various factors on the purchasing decisions of Millennials aged 27 to 42 in Metro Manila and Valenzuela. Emotional appeal emerged as a significant determinant, indicating that the emotional content embedded in YouTube advertisements resonates with this demographic and directly affects their intention to make a purchase. Similarly, content analysis, selective exposure behavior, credibility, and source attractiveness were identified as crucial elements in shaping Millennials' purchasing decisions. The study's findings underscore the multifaceted impact of YouTube advertisements, highlighting the importance of crafting emotionally resonant content, ensuring credibility, and leveraging source attractiveness to effectively target and engage the specified demographic.

Moreover, the study implies that YouTube's role extends beyond entertainment and education; it serves as a powerful platform influencing consumer behavior. The democratization of information and the accessibility of diverse content have transformed YouTube into a dynamic space where businesses can connect with their target audience. The research demonstrates that a compelling YouTube advertisement, combining emotional appeal, credible content, and an attractive source, has the potential to significantly sway the purchasing intentions of Millennials. As the digital landscape continues to evolve, understanding and harnessing the impact of these variables become essential for businesses seeking to thrive in an era where online platforms play a pivotal role in shaping consumer choices.

Recommendations

The findings of this study suggest that the YouTube commercial for strong dietary supplements has a significant impact on Millennials, influencing their purchasing intentions. The study identifies several key elements that play a role in attracting customers, including emotional appeal, trustworthiness, content analysis, selective exposure behavior, attractiveness source, and intention to buy.

The results highlight the effectiveness of YouTube advertising in promoting high-quality nutritional supplements and emphasize the importance of credibility, emotional appeal, and content techniques in influencing positive consumer choices. The study suggests that marketers can employ a multidimensional approach to gain a deeper understanding of the variables that contribute to the success of their advertising initiatives within the Millennial demographic.

One of the key findings is the relevance of the source of attractiveness, which encompasses likeability, familiarity, and similarity as source attributes. Familiarity refers

to knowledge of the source through exposure, similarity is the perceived likeness between the source and the message recipient, and likability is the affection for the source based on conduct, appearance, or other characteristics. The study indicates that customers often appreciate the physical attributes, artistic ability, and personalities of sources in both the product market and advertisements.

As the study concludes with the positive impact of YouTube advertising on Millennials' purchasing intentions, it may be beneficial to consider potential applications of these findings in marketing strategies. Marketers could leverage the identified elements such as emotional appeal, credibility, and source attractiveness to create more effective advertisements for dietary supplements targeting the Millennial demographic.

Additionally, future research could explore the generalizability of these findings to other samples or demographics. It may be valuable to conduct similar studies with larger samples or in different cultural contexts to assess the Brand Xness of the observed effects. Furthermore, researchers may want to investigate whether similar results can be achieved with different advertising approaches or platforms, expanding the understanding of effective marketing strategies in the realm of dietary supplements. If there are any unexpected or curious results, it would be prudent to recommend further research to verify the findings and explore potential reasons behind them.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declare that they obtained the participants' informed consent, the respondents' freedom to withdraw from the study at any time was made known to them, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

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Questionnaire

Greetings

We, the 4th year Marketing Management students from the College of Business and Accountancy of Our Lady of Fatima University - Valenzuela Campus, are now working on a quantitative research paper to complete the course requirements for Business Research In order to a **Assessing the Impact of Youtube Advertising for Dietary Supplements on Millennials' Purchase Intentions** , Our team will examine the answers of Male Millennials regards to the research taken.

Informed Consent

There is no risk to study participants other than their time commitments. On the other hand, it might be advantageous to you. The results could help you better comprehend and see things from a different angle regarding your current circumstance.

Given this, we cordially invite you to take part in the study. We sincerely abide by Republic Act No. 10173, so we can guarantee that your privacy will be completely protected. Only the researchers will have access to the information gathered, which will be kept in absolute confidence. We will never reveal your name or identity.

We are really grateful for your participation. Regards and Godspeed.

Screening Tool

Age *

- 27
- 28
- 29
- 30
- 31
- 32
- 33
- 34
- 35
- 36

- Quezon City
- Caloocan
- Manila
- Within Metro Manila
- Outside Metro Manila

- 37
- 38
- 39
- 40
- 41
- 42

Sex *

- Male

HAVE WATCHED ROBUST YOUTUBE ADS FOR THE LAST (2 Weeks) *

- Have watch
- Have not watch

Click the **"Watch on Youtube"** if your choice is "Have not watch"

After you watch the Youtube ads please proceed to the next section

Research Instrument and Likert Four-Point Scale Range Interpretation

EXPLANATION		
POINT	SCALE RANGE	EXPLANATION
4	4.00 - 3.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.99 – 2.00	Agree
2	1.99 – 1.00	Disagree
1	1.00 – 0.99	Strongly Disagree

Emotional Appeal *

4

3

2

1

The Youtube Ads made me feel like I would be healthier and more energized if I took the Brand X.

The Youtube Ads made me feel like taking the Brand X. would be a positive step towards achieving my health and wellness goals.

The Youtube Ads made me feel emotionally connected to the brand and its products.

Overall, The Youtube Ads made me more likely to purchase the Brand X

Credibility *

4 3 2 1

The production quality of The Youtube ads for th Brand X.e seemed high-budget and professional.

The visuals and sound effects used in the advertisement were impressive and engaging.

The advertisement featured well-known celebrities or influencers, making it seem

trustworthy.

The overall appearance of the advertisement conveyed a sense of prestige and quality for t|Brand X;t
e.

Content Analysis *

4 3 2 1

The YouTube ads for Brand X.e Supplements are visually appealing and engaging

The Youtube ads clearly communicate the benefits of using Brand X : Supplements.

The Youtube ads

target my interests and concerns related to health and well-being.

The Youtube ads feature testimonials from people who have seen positive results from using Brand X Supplements.

Selective Exposure Behavior *

4 3 2 1

I enjoy watching informative YouTube videos about health and wellness.

I actively seek out YouTube channels that offer valuable insights on healthy living.

I appreciate YouTube advertisements that educate me regards to health and wellness products.

I find myself engaging with YouTube advertisements for R₁ Brand X_{1e} that seem relevant to my health goals.

Source Attractiveness *

4 3 2 1

I find The Youtube Ads for Brand X₁ Ex Supplements to be visually appealing.

I enjoy watching The Youtube Ads for R₁ Brand X_{1e}

Supplements.

I believe the people featured in The Youtube Ads for Rebrand X. The Supplements are credible and trustworthy.

I feel a connection with the people featured in The Youtube Ads for Rebrand X. The Supplements.

Purchase Intention *

4 3 2 1

I am likely to try a Rebrand X. The Supplement after seeing an advertisement for it on YouTube.

I am willing to spend money on a

I am willing to spend money on a Brand X.t Ex supplement if I believe it will improve my health and well-being.

I am open to trying new Rr Brand X.1e supplements based on recommendations from Youtube ads.

I consider Youtube ads to be a reliable source of information about Rr Brand X.1e supplements

I am confident that I will make an informed decision when purchasing Brand X1 Ex supplement based on information I have gathered from Youtube ads.

Descriptives

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
DV Purchase_Intention	2.9460	.44572	100
IV Emotional_Appeal	2.9625	.47191	100
IV Content_Analysis	2.9875	.50173	100
IV Selective_Exposure_Behavior	2.9850	.51348	100
IV Credibility	2.8900	.44851	100
IV Source_Attraction	2.7850	.49622	100

Linear Regression Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.246	.315		3.956	<.001
	IV Emotional_Appeal	.002	.105	.002	.018	.986
	IV Content_Analysis	-.033	.094	-.038	-.357	.722
	IV Selective_Exposure_Behavior	.085	.098	.098	.862	.391
	IV Credibility	.158	.097	.159	1.633	.106
	IV Source_Attraction	.390	.107	.434	3.649	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: DV Purchase_Intention

Correlations

		DV Purchase_Intention	IV Emotional_Appeal	IV Content_Analysis	IV Selective_Exposure_Behavior	IV Credibility	IV Source_Attraction
Pearson Correlation	DV Purchase_Intention	1.000	.329	.272	.396	.389	.548
	IV Emotional_Appeal	.329	1.000	.507	.521	.302	.569
	IV Content_Analysis	.272	.507	1.000	.507	.300	.489
	IV Selective_Exposure_Behavior	.396	.521	.507	1.000	.401	.582
	IV Credibility	.389	.302	.300	.401	1.000	.466
	IV Source_Attraction	.548	.569	.489	.582	.466	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	DV Purchase_Intention	.	<.001	.003	<.001	<.001	<.001
	IV Emotional_Appeal	.000	.	.000	.000	.001	.000
	IV Content_Analysis	.003	.000	.	.000	.001	.000
	IV Selective_Exposure_Behavior	.000	.000	.000	.	.000	.000
	IV Credibility	.000	.001	.001	.000	.	.000
	IV Source_Attraction	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.
N	DV Purchase_Intention	100	100	100	100	100	100
	IV Emotional_Appeal	100	100	100	100	100	100
	IV Content_Analysis	100	100	100	100	100	100
	IV Selective_Exposure_Behavior	100	100	100	100	100	100
	IV Credibility	100	100	100	100	100	100
	IV Source_Attraction	100	100	100	100	100	100